

MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS OF SMALL BUSINESS ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. *Today, there is a growing interest in small businesses in our country. In particular, efforts are being made to boost the economy of such enterprises by providing them with various benefits. This article covers small businesses and their management systems. The organizational structure will be an important factor in the success of the enterprise, its ability to withstand competition, maintain or increase its capacity, and its ability to adapt to changing conditions.*

Keywords. *household, economy, market economy, income, employment, community, resource, small business, marketing, profit.*

The organizational structure will be an important factor in the success of the enterprise, its ability to withstand competition, maintain or increase its capacity, and its ability to adapt to changing conditions. The word "structure" is Latin and refers to the interconnected arrangement and structure of the components of things. a set of gins. Today, companies are trying to restructure their organizational structure and fully adapt their activities and functions to the needs of consumers.

In the 1990s, many companies around the world underwent unprecedented structural changes. The purpose of these changes is to increase the level of customer service, eliminate unnecessary management links, and create working groups to develop and produce new products. That is, the company adapts to the rapidly changing environment by overcoming organizational changes, overcoming fierce competition and increasing the efficiency of the enterprise.

Adapting a small business to market demand requires a comprehensive analysis of its vertical organizational structure. Based on the analysis, the restructured structure will conduct business at a high level, providing constant communication with all market participants. The organizational structure of the enterprise management is a holistic system of departments, specially designed links and relationships between employees, and the people working within it perform the task of achieving the goal in the most effective way. . In order for a small business to be effective, it needs to determine what kind of professionals it

needs, what skills it has, and what personal qualities it needs to bring together. The organizational structure of many businesses is constantly changing. Such changes are not limited to the transition from a vertical management system to a horizontal management system, but through these structures, businesses must be able to communicate effectively with all market participants and conduct effective business activities.

Organizational structures come in the form of management units and management levels. The following elements are distinguished in the structure of the enterprise: leadership and communication (horizontal and vertical) places (departments), levels (stages). The department is a separate, independent governing body. The main goal of the department (group of people) is to perform a certain task. Relationships between departments are horizontal. The connection between the steps is a vertical connection. They have a consistent subordination, freely expressed from the lower levels to the higher levels. In any, even a small enterprise, it is possible to determine the presence of all of the structural elements described above.

The entrepreneur is the owner of the company he founded and manages it. Vertically, it is subordinated to its employees. The vertical organizational structure consists of several levels of management that are interconnected. The management phase is a link that operates at a certain level of hierarchy. The control steps show the consistent subordination of one control joint to another, usually the lower joint to the upper joint, i.e., a vertical division. organizational structure of management, such as the structure of the stages and the order of their mutual subordination, the rights and duties of each governing body and link, as well as the order of relations between them, the creation of functional units, information provision The sides form a vertical control system. Agreeing on these in terms of content and timing will allow different services to connect many elements of production.

In some cases, such horizontal links between functional services can be very lengthy, subject to a number of disputes and conflicts, and can be very difficult to coordinate. It is known that the organizational divisions of business enterprises are formed on the basis of functional, geographical, commodity, market principles or through their joint application.

Businesses that are now operating effectively have as few management units as possible in their organizational structures, such as fulfilling orders, inventing new products, and planning production, distributing goods, and serving customers. pay great attention to processes. These businesses are reducing the number of management units, introducing a one-tier management system, and reducing the number of managers.

Horizontal links are established between employees of the company performing various functions (organizational marketing, accounting, etc.). They are not directly subordinate, but often determine the consistency and interdependence of the various production (practical) operations of the enterprise. The communication system means that all government agencies perform their functions in close cooperation with each other. Loss of connection means loss of control. Relationships can take many forms: linear (vertical), functional (horizontal), banded, and regional. The linear organization of management is based on the division of direct job responsibilities in such a way that each employee is most focused on the tasks facing the firm.

All powers are defined directly (linearly). They vary from top management to lower management. The linear-functional organization of the management structure combines both linear and functional management elements, ie linear management is strengthened by special ancillary services. The organizational structure of many businesses in the world is based on the business process, which retains the usual functional and specialized departments (human resources, research and marketing departments). Business processes include the production of new goods, the comprehensive processing of orders received, and other strategic directions. As the organizational structure based on these business processes is strengthened, some unnecessary management links will be reduced and working groups will be formed to develop new products that are competitive and adapt to the business environment.

The transformation of the organizational structure is constantly taking place in market conditions, with changes in competitors.

The following comparative characteristics of the organizational structure based on functional organizational structure and business process can be given:

1. Business process-based management requires managers with sufficient experience to solve complex problems.
2. Functional organizational structure requires staff with the skills to collect and analyze information and influence external audiences.
3. The organizational structure based on the business process, the establishment of relations between the parties leads to the elimination of conflicts, negotiations, management of information gathering, organization of working groups, training with high skill.
4. A company that adapts to market demand focuses on the consumer, not the product or technology.
5. Functional organizational structure requires employees to have a deep and thorough knowledge of their field, the ability to analyze and evaluate processes

and events, to be able to defend their recommendations and to convince others of it.

6. Lack of clear and responsible staff for the final results of the work of departments in the functional structure, it is advisable to use a combined (mixed) management structure to resolve business disputes between functional departments.

Conclusion

The organizational structure will be an important factor in the success of the enterprise, its ability to withstand competition, maintain or increase its capacity, and its ability to adapt to changing conditions. There are linear, linear-functional, projected and matrix, venture and intra-firm innovative organizational types of management structures of small businesses. Structural change is not only the transition from a vertical management system to a horizontal management system, but also the ability to operate effectively through these structures. Solving current problems in the activities of modern small businesses requires the coordinated use of several management structures of organizational types.

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